

Entrepreneurial Predisposition and Intention of Students from the IFRN - Mossoró, Brazil

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Abstract : IFRN - Mossoró is a Brazilian technical education institute that develops several activities to encourage entrepreneurship, such as a curricular discipline about enterprise management and the existence of a business incubator. Despite efforts, the business incubator does not produce the expected effects. Therefore, what predisposes students to start their own business? If literature review explores determinant factors like the family and personal characteristics, it can be sustained that entrepreneurship skills can be taught since primary level, until university level. This paper presents the results of research project "Empreende IFRN" to understand the entrepreneurial predisposition and intention of the students from technical level courses. Data from 365 students from technical level courses reveal an increased entrepreneurial intention of students during time (from a 2 years period to someday in the future). The entrepreneurial behaviour of parents affects students' perception about starting their own business. Students also present a cautious behaviour, preferring bank deposit and investment fund instead starting a business.

Keywords : Brazil, entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurship, secondary technical students

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